

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

OPTIMIZATION OF STATISTICAL INFORMATION ON OCCUPATIONAL INJURIES IN THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

Abikenova Sh.

*Candidate of Physical and Mathematical Sciences,
Research Institute for Occupational safety*

Abdrakhmanova N.

*Master of Engineering,
Research Institute for Occupational safety
Republic of Kazakhstan, Nursultan*

Abstract

This article provides information on state statistical reports on industrial injuries in a number of countries, such as the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Russian Federation, the Republic of Belarus, the Republic of Armenia and the Kyrgyz Republic. Also a comparative analysis of the forms of statistical reports of these countries was carried out, which showed that there are differences in some positions.

Keywords: industrial injuries, reporting, labor protection, statistical forms.

Introduction.

The need to use reliable statistical information in modern society is significantly and systematically increasing, taking into account the importance of effective management and decision-making. Based on statistical data, forecasts are made, conclusions are drawn and trends are determined. The solution of important tasks of statistical accounting and systematization of data meets the needs of digitalization of economic and production processes outlined in the program "Digital Kazakhstan"[1].

This article deals with the problem of using statistical information in the analysis of occupational injuries as the main indicator characterizing working conditions and occupational safety at enterprises.

Methodology

In the Republic of Kazakhstan, the main statistical information on occupational injuries is formed according to Form No. 7-TPZ, approved by the order of the Chairman of the Statistics Committee of the Ministry of National Economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 51 dated November 14, 2014. The basis for filling out this form is the act of an accident related to work, "Report on injuries related to work and occupational diseases"[2].

This state statistical reporting is submitted annually until February 25 after the reporting period, signed by the head of the enterprise [3].

The statistical form includes data on accidents that occurred at work with workers, employees, students and students during internship or work at enterprises, institutions, organizations of all forms of ownership. At the same time, all injuries, occupational diseases, poisoning and other negative health effects received during the performance of work duties, for which an investigation was carried out this year, are subject to accounting.

The section of the statistical reporting form contains information and the following information:

- the actual location of the legal entity (subdivision), as well as the name and code according to the

Nomenclature of types of economic activity (code according to OKED) of the legal entity[4];

- number and date of the accident report (occupational disease, poisoning);

- gender and age of the victim at the time of injury;

- the status of the victim from the Classifier of occupations[5];

- was there a shift job, indicating the shift in which the accident occurred;

- the physical condition of the patient at the time of the accident according to the conclusion of the forensic medical examination (alcohol and drug intoxication, mental disorder);

- type of injury;

- the affected part of the body;

- type of occupational disease;

- type of incident;

- list of causes of the accident;

- the severity of the victim's injury;

- the number of calendar and working days of disability;

- material consequences of an accident (payments on a disability certificate and lump-sum benefits).

Statistical reporting is provided in hard copy or in electronic format through the use of software posted on the Internet resource of the Committee on Statistics of the Ministry of National Economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan, which is the state authorized body in the field of state statistics.

At the same time, the Committee of Labor, Social Protection and Migration of the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Population of the Republic of Kazakhstan, as the state authorized labor body that generates statistical information on occupational injuries, in order to promptly collect information on occupational injuries, collects data according to the approved order of the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated 30.11.2015 No. 904 "On approval of the forms of acts of state labor inspectors" form[6].

At the same time, the analysis of statistical data from the two sources of official statistical information

mentioned above showed the presence of discrepancies in them. For example, by the end of 2021, according to the Bureau of National Statistics of the Agency for Strategic Planning and Reforms of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the number of victims at work amounted to 2,133 people, the number of deaths at work - 176 people. At the same time, according to the Labor Committee of the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Population of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the number of victims at work amounted to 1503 people, the number of deaths at work - 208 people. [7]. Thus, we believe that such differences in statistical data should not be attributed to calculation errors, seeing the reason in the concealment of data and the incompleteness of the information provided. The discrepancy in the data leads to a distortion of the current situation on occupational injuries.

Main part

In general, the use of existing methods of collecting statistical reporting and analyzing information does not objectively reflect the situation in the field of occupational safety and health.

In this regard, taking into account economic integration, the experience of processing similar statistical information in the countries of the Eurasian Economic Union, such as the Russian Federation, the Republic of Belarus, the Republic of Armenia, the Kyrgyz Republic, is interesting.

In the Russian Federation, the state statistical reporting on occupational injuries includes approved forms of state statistical observation "Information on injuries at work and occupational diseases" (Form 7 – injuries), "Information on the distribution of the number of victims of accidents at work by the main types of accidents and causes of accidents" (appendix to Form 7-injuries) [8]. The collection and processing of statistical information is carried out by Rosstat of Russia.

It should be noted that in the Russian Federation, statistical reporting forms cover legal entities, except microenterprises, of all forms of ownership, engaged in all types of economic activities, except financial activities, military security, social insurance, education, household activities.

A significant difference between the statistical reporting forms used in the Russian Federation is the complexity of the data collected in general for all cases of injuries that occurred at the enterprise in the reporting period.

So, in the specified form of statistical reporting No. 7-injuries, information about:

- the number of victims with disability for 1 working day or more, including fatally injured, including in the context of injured women, persons under the age of 18 and foreign citizens;
- the number of victims whose death occurred in the reporting year, regardless of the time of the accident, including injured women, persons under the age of 18 and foreign citizens;
- the number of working man-days of disability for victims with disability for one working day or more, whose temporary disability ended in the reporting year;
- the number of victims who have partially lost their ability to work and transferred from their main job

to another for 1 working day or more in accordance with the medical report, including women who have partially lost their ability to work;

- the number of persons with an occupational disease for the first time in the reporting year;
- the costs of labor protection measures, including the costs of improving working conditions and occupational safety at work, at the expense of all sources of financing;
- the average number of employees consisting of employees on the payroll and part-timers, including working women, consisting of employees on the payroll and external part-timers (without women on maternity leave and additional parental leave).

It follows that statistical reporting makes it possible to analyze occupational injuries for foreign citizens, as well as to estimate the costs of labor protection.

At the same time, along with the reporting form No. 7-injuries, 1 time in 3 years, legal entities provide an appendix to the annual statistical form No. 7-injuries, which indicates the distribution of victims by the main types of accidents that led to an accident at work and the distribution of victims by the causes of accidents.

Similarly, in the Republic of Belarus, the state statistical reporting provided in the form 1-t (injuries) "Report on the number of victims of industrial accidents" also contains general data on injuries. This form is presented by legal entities, their separate divisions having a separate balance sheet (until January 15) [9].

This report on the number of victims of industrial accidents reflects the following data:

- on the number of victims of industrial accidents with disability for 1 working day or more, including fatal victims, of which: a) women; b) persons under the age of 18, including: about the victims who were in a state of alcoholic, narcotic or toxic intoxication;
- on the number of fatal victims whose death occurred in the reporting year, regardless of the time of the accident, of which: a) women; b) persons under the age of 18, including: about the victims who were in a state of alcoholic, narcotic or toxic intoxication;
- on the number of days of disability of victims falling on working days, as well as days of disability of persons whose temporary disability lasted from the end of the previous year and was issued with one disability sheet, including in the context of affected women and persons under the age of 18.

It should be noted that the statistical reporting data do not allow for an economic analysis of occupational injuries.

Statistical reporting is provided on paper or in the form of an electronic document using specialized software on the official website of the National Statistical Committee of the Republic of Belarus.

In the Kyrgyz Republic, state statistical reporting is provided in the form No. 7-TVN "On occupational injuries, occupational diseases and material costs associated with them" is presented annually (on January 15th after the reporting period) [10].

The following information is reflected in Form No. 7-TVN:

- the number of victims with disability for 1 working day or more, including women;
- the number of fatalities, including women;
- the number of person-days of absences due to temporary disability related to injuries, including cases of accidents in the reporting year;
- the number of victims with partial disability and transferred in case of accidents, caused in accordance with the medical report to another job for one working day or more, of them women;
- the number of persons with a newly established occupational disease;
- costs of labor protection measures;
- expenses for the payment of damages in connection with labor injury and occupational disease, of which:

- a) temporary disability;
- b) indicating the reimbursed lost earnings;
- c) medical, social and vocational rehabilitation expenses;
- the cost of damaged equipment, tools, destroyed buildings, structures as a result of an accident.

Statistical reporting in the Kyrgyz Republic is provided only on paper by mail.

In the Republic of Armenia, the main form of the report on occupational injuries is the form of state statistical reporting 7-tvn, approved by the decision of the State Statistical Council of August 12, 2002 No.170-N. The report on occupational morbidity is submitted in Form 7 (occupational morbidity) [11].

Every year, by January 25, legal entities, enterprises, and private entrepreneurs send a report on the form 7-tvn on occupational injuries to the territorial bodies of the statistical service, which summarize the results of the reports submitted and send it to the Statistical Service of Armenia by February 15, where a report on the form 7 on occupational diseases is also sent to Medical social expert agencies.

Findings

A comparative analysis of the statistical reporting forms of the EAEU countries has shown that the forms of statistical reporting on work-related injuries and occupational diseases have some differences. An important distinguishing feature of the statistical forms used in the Russian Federation, the Republic of Armenia, the Kyrgyz Republic is the provision of comprehensive statistical information on all cases of injuries covering all legal entities of all forms of ownership.

Thus, having analyzed and evaluated the statistical reports of the EAEU countries represented, it can also be proposed to analyze the economic losses of the enterprise in connection with industrial accidents, including indirect ones; to assess the consequences of an industrial accident in the form of compensation payments.

Thus, in order to further improve and improve the quality of state statistical observations in the field of occupational safety and health, in particular occupational injuries, and to obtain complete and comprehensive statistical information, it is proposed:

1) provide reports on the whole enterprise;

2) include additional information in the forms:

- a) on the costs of labor protection measures, including the costs of improving working conditions and occupational safety at work;
- b) on the costs of payment of damages in connection with labor injury and occupational disease, including:
 - compensation for lost earnings;
 - expenses for medical, social and vocational rehabilitation.

These additions and changes will improve the statistical reporting system, optimize the procedure for providing reliable data, thereby improving the quality and facilitating the processing of information.

References

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2. Appendix 7 to the Order of the Chairman of the Statistics Committee No. 51 dated November 14, 2014 "Report on work-related injuries and occupational diseases".
3. "Instructions for filling out the statistical form of the national statistical observation "Report on work-related injuries and occupational diseases" (code 1381104, index 7-TPZ, annual frequency).
4. The nomenclature of types of economic activity (oked 5-digit) was approved by the order of the Chairman of the Agency of the Republic of Kazakhstan on Statistics dated May 20, 2008 No. 67.
5. Classifier of classes approved by the Order of the Committee of Technical Regulation and Metrology of the Ministry of Investment and Development of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated May 11, 2017 No. 130-od.
6. Order of the Ministry of Labor and Social Development of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated 30.11.2015 No. 904 "On approval of forms of acts of state labor inspectors".
7. Newsletter on the results of the activities of the Committee on Control, Social Protection and Migration in 2006-2015.
8. Rosstat Order No. 355 dated July 21, 2016 "On approval of statistical tools for the Organization by the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation of federal statistical observation in the field of health protection".
9. Resolution of the National Statistical Committee of the Republic of Belarus on June 13, 2016 No. 64 Form of State statistical reporting 1-t (injury) "Report on the number of victims in case of accidents at work".
10. Resolution of the National Statistical Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic dated June 7, 2016 No. 10 Form No. 7-TVN "On occupational injuries, occupational diseases and material costs associated with them".
11. The form of state statistical reporting 7-tvn, approved by the decision of the State Statistical Council of August 12, 2002 No. 170-N.